

Representation of Power, Intelligence, and Women Image in the Moxie Movie

(Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis)

Nurdin

(Master of Linguistics, Warmadewa University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT : *This research aimed to analyze the power, intelligence, and women image in the Moxie movie by using Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis by Teun Van Dijk. This research used Descriptive Qualitative Method. The source of the data in this study comes from the Moxie movie which was released in 2021. The data was collected through watching the movie carefully for several times, pausing every scene to read the conversation text, screenshooting the image that related, and taking a note about the data. This research is analyzed by identifying characters that represented the Power, Intelligence, and Women Image which focuses on text structure and social context, Displaying and interpreting the data about Power, Intelligence, and Women Image by using Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis theory by Teun Van Dijk as a grand theory and semiotic theory by John Fiske as a supporting theory, and Drawing the conclusion. The results in this research indicate that social movements carried out by women are an attempt to liberate equal rights between women and men. Power and Intelligence represented in the Moxie movie are efforts and determination to create an equal life which focuses on text structure and social context. The text structure sees gender inequality that occurs where women are always shown as weak creatures and are always blamed when there is a problem of violence against female students. The social context in the Moxie movie is shown by the phenomenon that is happening right now where when sexual violence occurs in a school, the victim does not dare to speak out because there is a lack of support from the school because it will bring a bad image to a school institution. In addition, the woman image represented in the Moxie movie is the Feminism movement in the form of women who can think intelligently, women have the reason to make decisions and every woman has the right to her body. Feminists want women to be free from oppressive gender roles.*

KEYWORDS -Technology, Discourse, Critical Discourse Analysis, Feminism, Semiotic, Movie

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology is the application of behavioral and natural sciences as well as other knowledge in a systematic and way to solve human problems. Technology has provided resources information and

communication that is very broad than what humans already have. The rapid development of technology is directly proportional to the development of mass media. Emergence of media recently changed the way people get information through the television. To be able to compete as a source of information that is of interest to the public, television media must carry out an innovation by means of convergence.

According to Deese (1984:72) through the meaning of media and discourse, it means the meaning of media content in the form of words, expressions of ideas conveyed by the media as a means of mass communication to society. The physical form of discourse is the contexts that are highlighted and discussed in the text of the media. So, the explanation is that discourse itself is closely related to language in linguistics.

Linguistic is a field of science that studies everything about language, form, function, meaning, value, and scientific discourse. In linguistics, discourse is a larger unit of language than sentences (Chaer, 2002:168). There are three central things in relation to the notion of discourse, namely text, context, and discourse. According to Nababan (1987:64) Language (text) is able to determine the context, because through language a person tries to influence others or demonstrate the power through the choice of words that are able to effectively manipulate the context. The discourse is the contained in a linguistic discipline, namely discourse analysis.

Discourse analysis is one of the fields of linguistic studies in the form of ways and methods to examine the existing discourse or contained in communication messages both textually and contextually. Discourse analysis in linguistic studies is a reaction to formal or more formal linguistic forms pay attention to units of words, phrases, and sentences without looking at the relationship between these elements. Discourse analysis is an effort to express hidden intentions of the subject who poses a question. The development of discourse analysis is not only centered on most news texts or media but also discourse analysis can see from the point of view of social reality contained in the movie.

Movie is a tool to convey various messages to the general public through a media story in the form of pictures and conversations. This then raises assumptions and opinions that movies have the potential to influence the audience. The audience who watched the movie carefully or even watching a movie many times intensely, will subconsciously accept the perspective and the new ideology contained in the movie that is witnessed is subtly and effectively. According to Surwati (2012:3-4), stated that movie is a tool to fulfill the pleasures of human. Women are only used as marginal parties and used in tragic soap operas, horror movies, and sexual-themed movies. In a discourse analysis there are many social problems, one of which concerns gender equality. Discourse and gender are two things that are usually debated by some people because they see social status, one of which is about Feminism.

Feminism is an ideology and a social movement to achieve equal rights for women in various ways. Equality in terms of political, economic, personal, and social rights can be interpreted in a broad ideology. This feminism is not based on liberalism which demands individualistic freedom and interests, moreover, feminism is based on Republican thinking where equality of rights is upheld regardless of social, educational, economic background, especially gender. One of the movie that has a big connection with a discourse analysis in the perspective of Feminism is the Moxie movie.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher used qualitative-descriptive method, which qualitative-descriptive research is a research method that described and depicted research objects based on facts that seem as they are by utilizing qualitative data and then described it descriptively. This research refers to the systemic analysis of Feminist ideology in the movie in terms of critical discourse elements and various sign meanings in the movie. This research was carried out by identifying the power, intelligence, and woman image in the Moxie Movie which was released in 2021. In the Moxie Movie, researcher sees various feminist discourses depicted with scenes by women. The researcher then carried out the data collection stage. The data collected was then analyzed using the established theory of Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis and Semiotic. The results of the data analysis are then conveyed through a descriptive description.

III. DISCUSSION

3.1 Text Structure

3.1.1 The power and intelligence depicted in the Moxie movie

In the context of mass media, language is the main element in the construction of reality. It is the main instrument for telling reality because language is able to become a conceptualization tool and a narrative tool in the media. According to media, language is not only a tool to represent reality, but also can determine and influence the meaning and picture that results from the reality that it constructs. As a means of communication, language does not escape its essence as a representation of ideology. In the context of Critical Linguistics, language is considered as a form of ideology. This can be seen from the focus research below:

3.1.1.1 Macro Structure Analysis

Macro structure analysis focuses on the main themes that dominate discourse. The theme or topic describes what the main idea or core message, which shows important information that the Moxie movie director wants to put forward or express. In the movie, the main topic or general theme taken by the researcher is the story of the reality of women which contains the issue of violence against women. Violence against women is an act of gender injustice in the form of physical and psychological violence. Violence is caused by the assumption that men hold supremacy and domination over various sectors of life. Violence against women in the Moxie movie has several levels, such as rape, discrimination, forced sterilization, and sexual harassment by touching or using expressions that demean women's dignity. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 1: Emma and Vivian stands on the pulpit and unite against the injustice experienced by female students
Duration:1:40:46

Vivian : And I mean, nobody does anything about it. Nobody listen to us. That's why I am standing up here. Yelling at all of you. It's why I started Moxie. You know what? If you're going to expel somebody, expel me, okay? It's me. I started Moxie. I am Moxie

Emma : I am the one who reached out for help because it felt like Moxie was the only one who was listening. Last year after prom, Mitchel Wilson raped me. He was my boy friend and he raped me in my own bedroom. And then, I got voted most bangabable. Sorry I don't know what to say. I don't know what I feel. I guess I'm just angry. I'm angry and I want to scream

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher analyzes that the power that is shown in this movie is when a girl who is on wheels still dares to come forward to share her opinion with Vivian, even when a girl named Emma claims to have been harassed by Mitchell in public, continues to fight for justice. Of course, this courage in being limited is commendable, because daring to be open to such problems is not easy, but with the support of the Moxie movement, Emma convinced herself to speak up. Patriarchy and sexism are hot issues and are currently being discussed, especially in the Moxie movie. Both of these things assume that women are inferior to men. In addition, this scene also explains patriarchy and sexism which was solved by the feminism movement, namely the need for awareness and change towards gender equality between men and women. This scene also emphasizes that women are not inferior and men are not superior, but both of them are equal.

This is supported by the statement issued by Vivian that Nobody listen to us. That's why I am standing up here, it means that Vivian is the driving force of the feminism movement so that she boldly invites her female students to leave school who does not care about sexual violence and sexism experienced by women. In accordance with the statement issued by Emma also that He was my boy friend and he raped me in my own bedroom, it means that she was a victim of sexual harassment by Mitchel Wilson, but with the feminism movement in Zine magazine, she dared to speak up because it was fully supported by all of her female friends

The second research focus is Intelligence. The intelligence depicted in the Moxie movie is in the form of interpersonal intelligence. Interpersonal intelligence itself is the ability to understand and cooperate with others, the ability to observe and understand the intentions, motivations and feelings of others. This intelligence is also able to enter into other people, understand the world of others, understand the views, attitudes of others and generally can lead a group. Intelligence in the Moxie movie is not just a discourse but an ideology which is essentially in the form of resistance, anti, and freedom from oppression, domination, hegemony, injustice, and violence experienced by women. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 2: Vivian starts to take action for creating a Zine magazine called Moxie movement

Duration:00:27:30

Vivian : Jesus. Stupid. I need a shitload of copies.
John : How many is that?
Vivian : Uh..fifty
John : Yeah, okay

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher sees that the intelligence shown by Vivian through the movie is that she secretly makes a magazine that contains a rejection of acts of violence and even discrimination in her school. This is clearly seen in the sentence uttered by Vivian that I need a shitload of copies. Vivian started to take action when her classmate named Kiera won the biggest ass in which the competition is made by male students at her school. Vivian was also inspired by her mother's activism, and began to secretly create a zine containing resistance to sexual harrasment at school, then distribute it throughout the school. The zine was named Moxie.

3.1.1.2 Superstructure (schematic) Analysis

Superstructure describes the general form of a text. The form of general discourse is arranged with a number of general categories or divisions such as introduction, content, conclusion, problem solving, closing and so on. According to Van Dijk, Schematics give emphasis which part comes first, and which part can be later as a strategy to hide important information. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 3: Claudia doesn't give support to the women's team

Duration:00:58:25

Vivian :Hey. Claudia. What is your deal? Why didn't you nominate her?
Claudia :What do you care. Just go back to your friends
Vivian :Is that what this is all about? You're mad I have a new friend?
Claudia : First, you don't just have one a new friends. You have a lot of friends.
Vivian : Why don't you care about this?
Claudia :I do. But making a big deal is not my thing

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher describes that Claudia thinks that everything that women should strive for will be in vain if they don't get support from the school. Female students are useless in providing support to their team leader if it is the male who manages all forms of victory in the baseball competition. Vivian didn't expect that Claudia would not really care about her friend of a

different race. It is clear in her sentence that says I do. But making a big deal is not my thing which Claudia doesn't want to put too much effort into making a big Feminism goal but the end result is a team of male students that will win. A phenomenon like this is a major conflict that has arisen between feminists in which one party doesn't overly promote its struggle for the other's female friends.

Feminism fights for justice and equality. If a feminist personally does not implement it from their closest circle, of course it is questionable the foundation of their idealism. This movie shows the audience that social change can be started alone, but must be driven together. Fighting alone will only provide a narrow perspective so that comprehensive changes will be difficult to make. On the other hand, if it is done together, apart from understanding each other fellow fighters, they will also get a more complete perspective on the social issues that must be handled.

3.1.1.3 Micro Structure Analysis

a. Semantic

The meaning that the researcher wants to emphasize in the Van Dijk scheme called the relationship between sentences and prepositions that build certain meanings in the discourse structure. Semantics in the Van Dijk scheme is categorized as a local meaning of the meaning that arises from the relationship between sentences, the relationship between proposals that build certain meanings in a text building. The meaning element looks at whether the text is conveyed explicitly or not, whether facts are presented nakedly or not. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 4: Vivian chases after Lucy

Duration:00:16:59

- Vivian : Look, I just wanted to say ignore Mitchell
Lucy : Why should I have to ignore him? Why can't he just not be a dick?
Vivian : He's an idiot. He has been since the second grade.
Lucy : He's dangerous
Vivian : I don't think he's dangerous. I think he's just annoying
Lucy : You know that annoying can be more than just annoying, right?. Like it can be code for worse stuff.
Vivian : If you keep your head down, he'll move on and bother somebody else
Lucy : Thanks for the advice. But, I'm gonna keep my head up, high.

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher analyzes that Through this scene the meaning that Amy Poehler as the director wants to convey with trying to introduce feminism to Generation Z, whose age range is still in their teens. Lucy, who is a girl of African-American descent, was reprimanded by Vivian to ignore Wilson's destructive behavior, but she firmly refused and would still fight the bully. This can be seen in Vivian's sentence which says that I don't think he's dangerous. I think he's just annoying which is the sentence spoken by Vivian is a representation of Intelligence that exists in the soul of a young feminist who has a strong determination to forbid the people she loves are not easily fooled by men.

In addition, the Power depicted in the movie scene above is shown by Lucy that a woman is not weak and will continue to fight if there is injustice and violence that they get from men. This can be seen clearly in the sentence that says But, I'm gonna keep my head up in which the sentence is actually a picture of the power of a feminist even though they are college students who still need protection from the school.

b. Syntax

1. Coherence

In discourse analysis, coherence is the affinity or connection between words, prepositions or sentences. Two sentences or prepositions that describe different facts can be connected using coherence, so that even unrelated facts can become related when the communicator connects them. Coherence is an element of discourse to see how someone strategically uses discourse to explain a fact or event. Are the events seen as separate, connected, or even causal. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 5: Vivian and Lisa are talking about the oppression that is carried out by the principal of student who wears tanktop at school

Duration:00:38:03

Vivian : Another girl had the exact same tanktop on. They were wearing the same thing, but she got in trouble because she looks a little different than that other girl.

Lisa : Oh. She had. Okay, I get it. Yeah

Vivian : Shelly was like "You gotta put on a sweater". She's like, "I don't have one". And so then Shelly said, 'come with me', and she sent her home

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher analyzes that The text above shows a causal event which is shown through the sentence expressed by Vivian They were wearing the same thing, but she got in trouble because she looks a little different than that other girl. The conjunction used in the

conversational text above is found in the word because which connects the sentence They were wearing the same thing, but she got in trouble with the sentence she looks a little different than that other girl so it looks coherent. Causal events are shown in the sentence she looks a little different than that other girl and the Effect is shown in the sentence were wearing the same thing, but she got in trouble. The coherence depicted in the scene of the movie is Intelligence shown by Vivian. This part is an Intelligence which shows Vivian's increasing anger when she begins to pay close attention to various policies at school as well as the behavior of the principal who is sexist and often discriminates against women. Vivian happens to have a mother figure who is always the place to tell stories, including about the hostile ecosystem at her school.

2. Sentence Form

The sentence form is a syntactical aspect related to logical thinking, namely the principle of causality. This sentence form determines whether the subject is expressed explicitly or implicitly in the text. Active sentences are generally used so that someone becomes the subject of their response, whereas passive sentences place someone as an object. Sentence form in the Moxie movie can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 6: Kiera and Amaya who are talking about racial discrimination that happened to them

Duration:00:43:05

Kiera : I don't like being voted Best Ass.

Claudia : You don't like it? Why?

Amaya : Historically, black women have been judged by their asses and hair, and we are done with that

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher analyzes that the text shown in the movie scene above is a passive sentence which is shown through the sentence spoken by Kiera black women have been judged by their asses and hair where black women at Rockport school have always been bullying by male students, especially Mitchell who is the student council president who always make a competition via social media related to black female students by making the selection of the best body shape that refers to sensitive areas. The objects of the commas above are Black women and access and hair are the subjects.

The intelligence that is depicted in the scene of the movie is when black women start to tell all forms of their frustration to their friends who are of a different race. This is also the beginning of their movement to start developing a good strategy so that all male friends and the school do not oppress them too much about the position of black women in school. So that Kiera, Amaya and their other friends began to think that justice could be obtained by all black women and especially also the white race who also experienced oppression.

3.1.2 Women Image Depicted in the Moxie Movie

Women image in the Moxie movie is described that women have reason to make decisions by drawing hearts and stars as symbols of resistance to gender. The published star and heart symbols contain elements of criticism by women. By drawing stars and hearts on their hands, it is hoped that gender equality efforts can spread love, a sense of joy and are expected to provide light and a bright path for other women in schools to continue to shine. It can be seen from the following picture and conversation:

Picture 7: Vivian and her friends supports feminism at school

Duration:00:35:01

Lucy : Good morning, and welcome to the revolution. Bam. Oh! Please tell me you did it

Vivian : Yeah. Do you like it?

Lucy : Yo. I took this picture and I started the hashtag “Moxie girl fight back”.

Based on the picture and conversation above, the researcher analyzes that uploads published through their social media invite community members' trust in one another to show the existence of the feminist movement. Women image in this movie scene can be seen in the sentence spoken by Lucy I took this picture and I started the hashtag “Moxie girl fight back” this shows the existence of women more and more real. Women are often ignored and left behind in making a decision. The thoughts of a woman are often not considered because of the stereotypes that exist in society, women's duties are only to be responsible and have a role in domestic or reproductive affairs, while men are in public or production affairs. Feminism is represented by women and intellectuals who can develop their abilities and make decisions. Feminism is also depicted through a woman who has a leadership spirit that is firm and careful when she becomes a leader. Because of this assumption, the main character in the Moxie movie, Vivian decided to create a zine that would be distributed anonymously in schools.

3.2 Social Context Depicted in the Moxie Movie

Social context looks at how the text is further connected with the social structure and knowledge that develops in society over one discourse. Therefore, the social context in this case is to answer the statement about how the discourse that develops in society regarding women.

In the Moxie movie, a form of verbal abuse and sexual abuse is shown by Lucy and Emma. Lucy has always been bullied by the head of the athletic team named Mitchell because of the difference of skin color and

they have always been considered a very different race from other women. Emma also experienced sexual violence committed by Mitchell by raping her even though the two were dating. Violence against women in the Moxie movie is an integral part of the phenomenon of violence in general. This relates to the position of women, which is completely second to none and which is full of taboos and stereotypes. The researcher assess that there are still many victims who do not have the courage to report because this case of sexual violence is still considered a disgrace in society.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, the researcher can conclude that there are feminist ideologies studied in this research, namely Power, Intelligence, and Women image. Power is depicted when female students in the Moxie movie decide to carry out a movement as a form of their protest against schools that turn a blind eye to the discrimination and sexual harassment that students receive. Intelligence is described when there is a rebellion by Vivian caused by things that are happening around her that contradict her logic. However, she was inspired by her mother, who also carried out the feminist movement when she was in school. The existence of this movie makes the audience more aware of how discrimination and sexual harassment can be fought with the feminist movement.

In addition, Women Image is depicted in this movie by looking at the level of reality of how women are presented in the media. The audience also knows that all women can carry out the feminist movement in their own way. In the Moxie movie namely making an anonymous zine as an initial form of resistance. The courage of a woman who dares to fight against the patriarchy in their school, dares to demand equal rights, dares to fight for justice for the rape that befell her friend, a woman who is able to balance her rational and emotional thoughts, a woman who is able to be a responsible leader, and strengthened by the action of women supporting women.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alkana, L., & Lerner, G. 1988. The Creation of Patriarchy. *The History Teacher*. <https://doi.org>
- [2] Barker, C. 2003. *Cultural Studies: Theory and Practice*. SAGE Publications.
- [3] Berberick, S. N. 2010. The Objectification of Women in Mass Media: Female Self-Image in Misogynist Culture. *The New York Sociologist*.
- [4] Brooks, D., & Hébert, L. 2006. Gender, race, and media representation. *Handbook of Gender and Communication*, 16, 297–317.

- [5] Fairclough, N. L. and Wodak, R. 1997. Critical discourse analysis. In T. A. van Dijk (ed.), *Discourse Studies. A Multidisciplinary Introduction*, Vol. 2. *Discourse as Social Interaction* (pp. 258–84). London: Sage
- [6] Van Dijk, T. A. 1991. *Racism and the Press*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- [7] Van Dijk, T. 1993. Principles of critical discourse analysis. *Discourse & Society*. <https://doi.org>.
- [8] Van Dijk, T. A. 1993a. *Elite Discourse and Racism*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- [9] Van Dijk, T. A. 1996. Discourse, power and access. In R. C. Caldas–Coulthard and M. Coulthard (eds), *Texts and Practices: Readings in Critical Discourse Analysis* (pp. 84–104). London: Routledge and Kegan Paul